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**FROM SHADOW EDUCATION TO HOLISTIC STUDENT
DEVELOPMENT: INTRODUCING DANISH LEISURE TIME PEDAGOGY
IN UZBEKISTAN'S SECONDARY SCHOOLS**

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***Annotation.** This article examines the growing phenomenon of shadow education in Uzbekistan and its impact on secondary school students' holistic development and mental well-being. The authors compare the highly competitive and exam-oriented Uzbek education system with the Danish model of leisure-time pedagogy, which emphasizes creativity, self-exploration, social interaction, and inclusive personal growth. The study highlights how excessive dependence on private tutoring in Uzbekistan limits students' opportunities for emotional, social, and creative development. Drawing on the Danish experience, the article proposes the introduction of leisure-time programs in Uzbek secondary schools as an alternative approach to reducing academic pressure and promoting balanced student development.*

***Keywords:** Shadow education, leisure-time pedagogy, holistic development, secondary education, academic pressure; private tutoring.*

***Аннотация.** В данной статье рассматривается растущее явление теневого образования в Узбекистане и его влияние на всестороннее развитие и психологическое благополучие учащихся средних школ. Авторы сравнивают ориентированную на экзамены и высокую конкуренцию систему образования Узбекистана с датской моделью педагогики свободного времени, которая делает акцент на творчестве, самопознании, социальном взаимодействии и гармоничном развитии личности. Исследование показывает, что чрезмерная*

зависимость от частного репетиторства в Узбекистане ограничивает возможности учащихся для эмоционального, социального и творческого развития. Опираясь на опыт Дании, авторы предлагают внедрение программ свободного времени в средних школах Узбекистана как альтернативный подход к снижению академического давления и поддержке сбалансированного развития учащихся.

Ключевые слова: Теневое образование, педагогика свободного времени, всестороннее развитие, среднее образование; академическое давление, частное репетиторство.

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada O'zbekistonda keng tarqalib borayotgan "shadow education" - ya'ni xususiy qo'shimcha ta'lim tizimi hamda uning o'rta maktab o'quvchilarining har tomonlama rivojlanishi va ruhiy salomatligiga ta'siri tahlil qilinadi. Mualliflar O'zbekistonning imtihon va raqobatga yo'naltirilgan ta'lim tizimini Daniyaning bo'sh vaqt pedagogikasi modeli bilan solishtiradilar. Daniya modeli ijodkorlik, o'zini anglash, ijtimoiy muloqot va shaxsning uyg'un rivojlanishiga katta e'tibor qaratadi. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, O'zbekistonda repititorlikka haddan tashqari bog'liqlik o'quvchilarning emotsional, ijtimoiy va ijodiy rivojlanish imkoniyatlarini cheklamoqda. Daniya tajribasiga asoslanib, maqolada O'zbekiston maktablarida bo'sh vaqt dasturlarini joriy etish akademik bosimni kamaytirish va o'quvchilarning muvozanatli rivojlanishini qo'llab-quvvatlashning muqobil usuli sifatida taklif etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Soyaviy ta'lim; bo'sh vaqt pedagogikasi, har tomonlama rivojlanish, o'rta ta'lim, akademik bosim, xususiy repititorlik, o'quvchilar farovonligi.

The education system in Uzbekistan faces a significant challenge due to the prevalence of shadow education – private supplementary tutoring parallel to formal schooling. This phenomenon reveals a loss of confidence in public schooling system and overemphasis on academic performance of secondary schools' students at the expense of student welfare and self-exploration period. In contrast, Danish leisure-time pedagogy or after-school programs offer holistic alternatives. These are based on the development of self-exploration, creativity, and an inclusive approach, rather than performance and competition, so widely present in the formal school system of Uzbekistan.

Despite the large number of studies that have been conducted on the effects of shadow education on the academic performance of Uzbek school students, there is very little research into its implications for students' holistic development and mental health. Furthermore, although Denmark has been highly praised for its leisure time programs and student-centered approach, little research has been done to investigate how these practices can be integrated into the Uzbek secondary school system. This gap focuses on the need for focused research on how the integration of leisure programs in secondary schools in Uzbekistan could ease the burden of shadow education and promote self-discovery and balanced development.

Globally, private supplementary tutoring, widely known as shadow education, has grown significantly both in scale and in intensity over the last decades, and students all over the world take part in a multitude of structured academic activities after ending their formal school day (Aurini Mikkelsen and Gravesen 547et al., 2013; Park et al., 2016; Yung & Bray, 2017). Similarly, in Uzbekistan, private tutoring has become a defining feature of its education system nowadays. Once a student enters the secondary class, parental focus increasingly shifts towards ensuring their child acquires adequate knowledge to excel in the high-stakes university entrance examinations upon completing school education. For many families, especially for middle-class families, education is a brutal race for a limited place set aside for winners who would be labeled successful social elites (Zhang, 2021).

In Denmark, by contrast, family investment in tutoring is more concerned with the children's internal needs for personal development than external pressures to excel or remain ahead in comparison with others (Zhang, 2021). An emerging anti-authoritarian school system and child-centered pedagogy from 1960s and onward has significance on the view of Folkeskole's (Denmark public school system) overall mission and pedagogic practices. The primary focus of Folkeskole is not limited only to fostering students academically; it places even greater emphasis on helping them become well-rounded individuals in a global society.

While reflecting those democratic notions, the Danish welfare society also has a firm tradition of leisure time pedagogy, evenly based on institutional practices and pedagogical values (Mikkelsen & Gravesen, 2021). The idea of Danish leisure time programs goes back to ground-breaking thoughts of Enlightenment philosophers, such as Jean-Jacques Rousseau who marked childhood as a separate and special world – “a world in which (the notion of) pleasure and freedom became integral elements of an increasingly less restrictive and less authoritarian pedagogical norm” (Mikkelsen & Gravesen, 2021). Despite the fact that Kindergartens are suited for younger children, the idea of giving space for natural growth and respecting the child’s free, independent development combined with giving access to adequate materials and promoting dialogue inspired and formed the Danish leisure-time pedagogy and the approach toward older children and young people too (Ankerstjerne, 2010). Leisure time programs in Denmark not only offered a safe space for children and youth to spend their time after school but also emphasized specific pedagogical values. These included the development of indoor and outdoor environments designed to encourage cultural and creative engagement, as well as fostering friendships and a sense of community. Initially, these services primarily targeted vulnerable and at-risk children and adolescents to keep them away from streets. However, from the 1960s onward, they became more mainstream, catering to all children and young people across Denmark. In order to protect young people’s right to free time and self-initiated activities, apart from formal, compulsory and adult-organized school, Denmark developed leisure time programs that reflect the opposite values: informal group activities for self-exploration and exchange of perspectives. Although not every child or young person attends an after-school program, the nonformal philosophies and values of voluntariness apply to the leisure sphere in general—a time for relaxing and/or doing whatever one likes to do. In addition to the pedagogical after-school programs, the Danish society has a long-standing tradition of sports and leisure associations driven by volunteerism, and today, according to research conducted by the National Council for Children in Denmark, 67% of Danish students in the ninth grade voluntarily partake in a leisure-time activity

in their after-school hours (Børnera°det, 2019). They participate not out of obligation but out of genuine enjoyment.

In Uzbekistan, where all emphasis is solely placed on academic excellence and preparation for highly competitive university entrance examinations, shadow education has become a fairly important phenomenon. While aspiring to help students close their academic gaps, this phenomenon has inadvertently created an environment where students' mental health and general well-being is being neglected. Due to the fact that the amount of pressure on students in academics outsteps even the ability of a public-school system, a growing disconnect has developed in the process of formal education and holistic development for students. In many cases, this narrow focus on academics often bars the way for students seeking activities through which they would foster personal, social growth and development, creativity, and a sense of community with others. While the focus on academic excellence remains essential, it must not come at the cost of students' ability to develop personally, socially, and emotionally.

To address these challenges, there is an urgent need for alternative approaches that can ease the after-school academic pressure of Uzbek secondary school students, while promoting self-exploration and social cohesion. This can be achieved with the implementation of Danish-style leisure time pedagogy which prioritizes social extra-curricular activities, sports, and cultural engagement.

Methodology

The purpose of this study is to gauge perceptions from students and parents in an attempt to assess the current impacts of shadow education and the possible benefits of introducing Danish leisure-time programs within secondary schools of Tashkent city as an initial pilot project. The data will be gathered by using two different questionnaires, targeting Uzbek secondary school students and parents, with questions concerning their attitudes toward the academic stress caused by shadow education and how leisure-time programs might benefit holistic student development.

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